

OUTCOME OF THE TESTING ON HOSPITAL SYSTEMS INTERFACE MODULES

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AMPLE	Allergies, Medications, Past medical history, Last meal, Events
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
eCREAM	Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction
ED	Emergency Department
EHR	Electronic health record
EU	European Union
GB	Giga Byte
HL7	Health Level Seven
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IRFMN	Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Italy
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KB	Kilo Byte
LIS	Laboratory Information System
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PDF	Portable Document Format
RAM	Random Access Memory
RIS	Radiology Information System
SFTP	SSH File Transfer Protocol
SSH	Secure Shell
TLoC	Transient Loss of Consciousness
TXT	Text
UC1	Use Case 1
UC2	Use Case 2
WP	Work Package
VPN	Virtual private network
ZIP	Compressed file format

Introduction

This document presents the results of testing the hospital system interface modules developed for the eCREAM project. Initial tests were conducted on the first installation at S.G. Bosco Hospital in June 2024, using sample data in a test environment.

The document will also cover the results obtained from production data from Turin. The tests carried out at some hospitals, the difficulties encountered in this phase of the project, and the methods of interaction with information systems and software houses are also described, as well as corrective activities applied by Astir to retrieve data from PDF files (radiology, laboratory, and other records) to ensure privacy.

1. Objectives of the WP2

The objective of WP2 is to develop and validate a data extraction tool that retrieves the required information from ED health records (including both the current EHRs and the new ED-EHR) and other hospital administrative databases. Specific objectives of WP2 include:

- analysing the operational and technological environment of participating EDs.
- mapping essential data to address use cases described in Pillar 4 and WP4 with information available in existing EHRs and the new ED-EHR.
- developing and testing modules that interface the eCREAM database with hospital systems.

The activities of T2.6, 'Development of Interface Modules on the Hospital Systems Side and Technical Support,' began in parallel with those of T2.5, 'Development of Interface Modules on the eCREAM Side'. The first installation at San Giovanni Bosco Hospital confirmed that all required information could be successfully retrieved from the hospital's medical records and that the hardware met the necessary requirements. This allowed the specifications to be shared with the information systems and vendors of other hospitals, where the ethics committees had approved the initial protocol.

The solution developed by Astir is highly versatile, enabling the retrieval of necessary information through batch transfers, regardless of the data format. The system gathers information from PDF, CSV or JSON files extracted from hospital medical records, which are locally stored and processed to populate the eCREAM data model.

The task of the deliverable involves the sharing of the necessary specifications for data export with the suppliers of the hospital information systems, the development of interfaces by the software suppliers, joint testing and support in the event of problems.

2. Testing of existing hospital systems interface

2.1 Introduction

A standardized approach was defined and structured into three main phases:

- **Initial information gathering:** Each hospital completed a questionnaire providing details about their local information systems, updated as of 2021. The data included the type of software in use for Emergency Departments, Laboratory Information Systems (LIS), and Radiology Information Systems (RIS), along with the respective vendors.
- **Introductory meetings:** All participating hospitals were contacted to organise an initial meeting to understand the specific needs of the project, assess the level of autonomy for data extraction and collect relevant contacts for a subsequent technical meeting with system suppliers.
- **Technical analysis:** During these meetings, the data extraction specification format was reviewed and discussed, to identify potential critical issues related to the installation of local components, security requirements, and the availability and accessibility of the required data. A first test track containing sample data was produced to verify the quality of the data.

Of all the hospitals contacted, only one declared full autonomy in data extraction without the support of external vendors.

The need to involve third-party vendors for this activity proved to be a critical factor, causing delays in the deliverable due to the time required to complete administrative procedures, i.e. the formalization of requests for quotations, which involve internal approval steps and consequently extend the overall timeline.

The image below shows the number of hospitals in each stage of the project progress, based on the three protocols, as of August 2025.

Figure 1. Project progression

Switzerland (CH) appears in red because activities were initially carried out but later interrupted due to the facility’s decision to no longer participate in the project.

2.2 Sharing of specifications

A unified method, applicable to all NLP-DeVAL, UC1, and UC2 protocols, was designed for extracting data from the hospitals involved in the project.

A time frame was selected (2021, 2022, and 2023) to enable the extraction of data useful for all protocols in a single process, following the 'one extraction, multiple use cases' approach.

Figure 2. 'One extraction, multiple use cases' approach

All activities carried out in the hospitals start with the initial sharing of specifications and hardware requirements through virtual meetings with the IT department and their suppliers.

Data collection, which can happen only after the ethics committees’ approval, is preceded by several preliminary activities carried out by each hospital involved in the project, Astir and IRFMN. Specifically:

- The Hospital IT staff provides:
 - the hardware required to install the local eCREAM component and to store the data extracted from the emergency department records.
 - A VPN channel enables Astir to perform installation and maintenance tasks and provides a secure environment for data export and transfer.
- Astir performs the installation of the "eCREAM Hospital Client" in the hospital’s eCREAM Local Platform
 - The hospital performs data extraction. It can be done directly from the hospital’s IT department, if it has the expertise, or externally by the software House, if the data extraction requires additional development.

The activities described above are shown in the figure below:

Figure 3. Activities and specific tasks

2.3. Definition of the infrastructural minimum requirement

The first data extraction at the S.G. Bosco Hospital verified the adequacy of:

- The specifications of the proposed hardware
- The size needed for filesystem and database
- The timing of the migration procedure from files received in Local eCREAM to the eCREAM data model (as described in “Annex 3_D2.2 - eCREAM Application Interface Specifications UC1 and UC2”).

The initial installation confirmed the minimum requirement that was defined in the analysis phase:

- CPU: 8 Core
- RAM: 32 GB
- Local drive: 50 GB
- External drive: 250 GB

The operational phase enabled the calculation of the space required for a shared software installation in case of multiple hospitals (about 31 GB).

The average storage space occupied by a single episode (about 310 KB) provided a reference for estimating capacity. By multiplying the average space of a single case, the number of cases and the number of facilities, it is possible to estimate the total storage space requirement by possibly refining the 250 GB space defined as the minimum requirement so that it fits the operational needs of each hospital.

2.4. Definition of the tests

To ensure that the data extracted from hospital clinical records complies with the data specification, a series of tests and validations were implemented. They include syntactic and semantic validation tests, completeness and internal consistency checks, domain and code verification, as well as structural conformity checks against the technical specifications of the data format.

Conformity to Data Specification

These tests verify the structural compliance of the data with the technical specifications defined in the eCREAM data schema.

Syntactic Validation Tests

These tests ensure that the data conforms to the expected format.

- Validation against the expected schema (e.g., JSON Schema validation)
- Data type checks (e.g., integers, dates, booleans, strings)
- Field length validation
- Date format validation (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD)
- Identifier format validation (e.g., ICD codes, national classification codes)
- Verification of proper delimiters (for CSV, JSON, etc.)

Completeness Checks

These tests verify that all mandatory fields are present and properly populated.

- Mandatory fields are not null
- All required sections of the dataset are present (e.g., demographic, clinical data, etc.)
- Conditional fields are validated based on context-specific logic

Domain and Value Set Validation

These tests ensure that field values belong to predefined and authorized code sets.

- **Standard code systems:** e.g. Diagnosis_Code must belong to the official classification in use; Procedure_Code must be listed in the regional or national tariff nomenclature
- **Enumerated values:** e.g. the Sex field must contain only "M", "F", or "Other"; the Discharge_Mode field must only contain valid, authorized values

Uniqueness Constraints

These tests verify that fields expected to be unique do not contain duplicates.

- the Episode_ID must be unique across all records of the same ED in the same year, such as the request ID code for the diagnostic tests

Internal Consistency and Semantic Validation

These tests verify logical consistency between fields. For example:

- Discharge date must be equal to or later than the admission date
- Clinical conditions must be compatible with patient sex or age
- Discharge mode must be compatible with the discharge status

Clinical Plausibility Checks

These tests ensure that values, while syntactically and semantically valid, are also clinically realistic and credible within the medical context.

2.5. Outcome of the testing with existing hospital systems

This chapter contains subsections corresponding to the hospitals available to organize data recovery so far. In each section the tests performed, the specific interventions carried out, and the results are reported.

The interactions with the suppliers of the hospitals of Turin, Policlinico of Milan, and Vercelli have resulted in some modifications and improvements in our specifications.

2.5.1. Outcome of the testing on S.G. Bosco Hospital in Turin

The Ethics Committee of the S.G. Bosco Hospital, the project's coordination centre, has approved all protocols. The hospital was the first to perform data extraction in a production environment. The collaboration with the hospital's Information Systems team and with the data providers of the emergency department helped define the data delivery format.

Data is extracted from the emergency department medical records in JSON format, which includes the entire patient journey within the emergency department and links to the order fulfilment systems (RIS, LIS and other medical records) where the services were provided. Information related to the RIS, LIS and other medical records reports, such as radiology reports, laboratory test results and other clinical documentation, is provided in PDF format. The request field is the link between an ED's episode and services such as radiology, laboratory, and others performed in external systems; it is created by concatenating the EHR event and the request number generated by the ED system when an exam is booked in an external system (RIS, LIS, or other EHR).

Listed below are the tests performed, the problems encountered, and the optimisations made to make the extraction possible and to import the data from the ED-EHR into the eCREAM data model described in “Annex 3_D2.2 - eCREAM Application Interface Specifications UC1 and UC2”.

The meetings organized with the hospital IT and the EHR system providers enabled the establishment of a collaborative dialogue. It allowed the optimization of the data extractor developed by the software vendor and improvements to the Local eCREAM component developed by Astir. Below is a list of the main issues encountered, the various steps and the approach adopted to address them.

First Proposed Data Set

Some initial test extractions were provided, revealing that certain entities required by the specifications (“Annex 3_D2.2 - eCREAM Application Interface Specifications UC1 and UC2”) were not included in the ED’s episode data. Specifically, the following elements were missing:

- **pathAssignment:** information on the patient’s pathway assignment within the ED
- **revaluation:** reassessment of the patient's triage priority level
- **otherTestList:** additional tests performed during the ED visit
- **pharmaceuticalTherapy:** prescription and administration of pharmacological therapy
- **respiratorySupport:** start and end dates/hours of respiratory support
- **monitoring:** start and end dates/hours of patient monitoring.

Some syntactic issues were also encountered in the JSON structure. Specifically, the tag “id” was used in place of “idObject”. The “idObject” tag is intended to uniquely identify a dependent object within the same request (e.g., multiple procedures performed at different times within a single request). Additionally, in the sample extraction provided, the “idObject” and “idRequest” fields were inverted.

In the JSON data containing the Emergency Department access episode, it was also necessary to clarify the notation used to link Laboratory and Radiology reports provided in PDF format. Specifically, the filename was defined as a concatenation of:

<ORGANIZATION_CODE>_<YEAR>-<NUMBER_ACCESS>_<ID_EXAMINATION>.pdf

- NUMBER_ACCESS = the numeric part of “episodeld” without the year
- ID_EXAMINATION = the ED internal examination code
- requestId = the laboratory/radiology request number

A problem was also reported regarding the loss of formatting (encoding) and special characters in text fields (e.g., medical history notes) during the JSON extraction.

The reported issues led the software vendor to correct the errors and provide a new data extraction. This updated version resolved the previously identified syntactic problems and served as the basis for further analysis, as described below. Additional clarifications were requested, which led to the following outcomes:

- **pathAssignment and pathCode**

The “pathCode” field within “pathAssignment” does not represent the clinical pathway (e.g., Fast Track or High/Medium/Low Intensity) but rather refers to the hospital department where the patient is examined, leading to potential ambiguity in interpretation. A mapping table was provided to correctly interpret the values in “pathCode”.

- **triageDateTime, edPathAssignmentDateTime, edArrivalDateTime**
The three timestamps are identical because, according to the current operational workflow, ED arrival, triage, and path assignment occur simultaneously.
- **dischargeDecisionDateTime and dischargeDateTime**
While often the same, these two fields serve distinct purposes:
 - “dischargeDecisionDateTime” is populated only for patients admitted and corresponds to the date the admission is scheduled — a necessary value for calculating boarding time.
 - “dischargeDateTime” indicates the actual time of discharge.
In the operational flow, the EHR populates “dischargeDecisionDateTime”, which is copied into “dischargeDateTime” only in case of admission. For all other patients, “dischargeDecisionDateTime” remains empty.
- **medicalVisit**
This field represents the first medical examination performed and marks the beginning of the patient’s clinical management by a physician. It precedes any subsequent specialist consultations.
- **See&Treat and nursingCareStart**
See&Treat pathways are not managed in the data structure, and the nursingCareStart field does not reflect such pathways.
- **Unmanaged Data**
The fields “medicalProcedure”, “pharmaceuticalTherapy”, “respiratorySupport”, and “monitoring” are not managed — that is, they are either unused or not implemented — within the ED-EHR.

Estimated Data Volumes

Volume estimates were carried out before proceeding with the actual extractions to assess the required storage space. The following figures were provided:

year/ Indicator	2021	2022	2023
ED Accesses	56,385	63,122	68,914
RIS Reports	43,291	44,581	46,015
LIS Reports	54,086	62,396	62,294
Other Reports	629	671	642
Specialist Consultation Reports	12,539	12,701	13,352
Vital Signs	22,399	23,126	57,476
Diary Notes	340,302	355,864	369,550

Figure 4. Estimated Data Volumes

The NLP-DeVAL protocol is based on free text data extraction from clinical notes, for the years 2021, 2022 and 2023. This data will be used to train the NLP language model.

The following table shows the data successfully collected from the first hospital in Italy to implement the eCREAM platform and is consistent with the estimates initially provided. We acquired approximately 1.8 million notes from a single ED over three years.

The extracted notes were categorized by type, with most of the information coming from triage assessments, discharges, nursing notes and clinical diaries.

Below is a summary of the extracted data:

EXTRACTED DATA	2021	2022	2023
UNIQUE EPISODES	56,385	63,122	68,914
ANAMNESIS	55,199	60,908	66,218
TRIAGE	112,757	126,239	137,817
MEDICAL_VISIT	53,864	59,079	64,199
DISCHARGE	107,217	117,470	128,187
NURSING_CARE_NOTES	107,932	119,045	110,916
CLINICAL_DIARY	118,804	110,900	122,812
HOME_BASE_THERAPY	5,253	5,181	5,405
SPECIALIST_CONSULYANCY	13,539	11,701	13,352

Figure 5. Extracted data

The data aggregated by year was compressed into ZIP files and transferred to the SFTP server installed at IRFMN. This process was completed during the first week of October 2024.

The data obtained enabled further analysis, which led to an additional evaluation.

Management of Multiple Procedures Within a Single Request

The structured data exported from the ED-EHR also includes PDF reports originated from external systems (LIS, RIS, OTHER). This corresponds to **Case A** described in the delivered specifications, where the JSON structure includes, in addition to the request identifier (requestId), metadata for each individual procedure (e.g., code, description, request/execution dates and times).

The ED-EHR allows multiple procedures to be associated with a single request, which results in a single cumulative PDF report. The agreed solution to represent this scenario involves keeping the “requestId” unchanged and distinguishing the individual procedures within the request using the “idObject” field. This led to the formalization of **multiple procedures** within a single request — for example, a radiology request may include several individual procedures.

Procedure Coding

The codes received for procedures requestable from the Emergency Department (laboratory and radiology) were analysed to assess their correspondence with the national or regional nomenclature. This analysis aimed to normalize the description of the procedures performed.

Anonymisation of Laboratory and Radiology Data in PDF Format (Not in JSON Text)

A total of 300,000 radiology and laboratory reports were processed and delivered in PDF format. To ensure data integrity and compliance with privacy regulations, the full text was extracted from the PDFs and subsequently processed using an anonymization tool.

To provide additional security to the anonymization tool used, ensuring reliable identification and removal of all other sensitive information contained in the reports that could be traced back to individual patients (such as birth dates, patient IDs, exam dates), Astir implemented custom regular expressions (regex). The regex allows for effective detection and removal of such data.

Below is a simplified diagram illustrating the entire process:

Figure 6. Anonymisation process of Laboratory and Radiology Data in PDF Format

Specifically:

- PDF files are converted to plain text files “1 – PDF to TXT”
- The custom regular expressions given under block “2 - RegEx processing” are applied to text data. If a regular expression matches a sensitive string, the entire corresponding text note is stripped to ensure maximum privacy
- The resulting dataset is then processed using the anonymization tool (AnonymAI) “3 – AnonymAI processing”.

The images below describe the process carried out.

Figure 7. RegEx

OUTCOME OF THE TESTING ON HOSPITAL SYSTEMS INTERFACE MODULES

██████████ Deleted by AnonymAI
██████████ Not Deleted by AnonymAI

DELETED THIS SECTION

KEEP THIS CLINICAL NOTE

DELETED THIS SECTION

Figure 8. Deleted and not deleted text by AnonymAI

A quality assurance process was performed to validate the effectiveness of anonymization, comparing the source PDF with the processed output and verifying personal identifiers had been successfully removed.

Regione **LUOGO**
 AZIENDA SANITARIA LOCALE CITTA' DI **LUOGO**
 Ospedale **LUOGO**
 RADIOLOGIA NEURORADIOLOGIA
 Direttore Dott. **NOME_PERSONA**
PHONE NUM.

Paziente: **NAME**
 Data di nascita: ██████████ ID Paziente: ██████████
 Numero archivio: ██████████ Data Esame: ██████████
 Provenienza: PS MEDICO DI BASE Acc. Num.: ██████████

TC ENCEFALO
 L'esame è stato confrontato con un precedente controllo del 5.4.22, rispetto al quale in noto idrocefalo, è sostanzialmente invariato il volume del sistema ventricolare in presenza di catetere derivazione ventricolo-peritoneale con apice distale a livello della cella media del ventricolo laterale dx. Si osserva diffusa ipodensità della sostanza bianca periventricolare con riassorbimento subependimale. Le strutture della linea mediana sono in asse. Non sono comparse lesioni focali encefaliche acute.

Informazione relativa all'esposizione
 Classe di dose secondo l'art. 161 del D. Lgs. 101/2020, usando il sistema di calcolo VirtualDoseCT: II
 Total DLPHEAD (mGy·cm): 1153.95

T.S.R.M. ██████████ TEC. **NAME** ██████████ DOTT. **NAME**

"Referto firmato digitalmente ai sensi delle norme vigenti
 D.P.R. n. 513 del 10/11/1997 D.P.C.M. del 08/02/1999
 D.P.R. n. 445 del 08/12/2000 D.L.G. del 23/01/2002"

La documentazione radiologica è disponibile su richiesta presso il Servizio di Radiologia Pagina 1 di 1

Figure 9. Comparison of source PDF with processed output

In this table is the summary of the data processed:

DATA	2021-2022-2023
RIS	123.188
LIS	175.670
OTHER_TEST	1.456

Figure 10. Summary of the data processed

The quality of the result made it possible to assume that this process will also be applied to all future installations that will provide data containing PDF reports.

For UC1, the classification of patients with a main clinical problem of Dyspnea and TLoC is expected.

Patient classification TLoC

Analysis of data collected at Turin Hospital reveals problems in identifying cases of TLoC (transient loss of consciousness), which, together with cases of dyspnea, are the only ones to be used for UC1.

Unfortunately, for TLoC, there is no clear classification of the primary clinical problem, and generic codes are often applied (such as “Other symptoms or disorders,” “Acute neurological syndrome,” or “Other nervous system symptoms”). This poses a twofold risk: on the one hand, the failure to recognize TLoC during triage; on the other, the inclusion of false positives.

Checks are being carried out on the original dataset to identify the correct TLoC cases.

2.5.2. Outcome of the testing at Lugano’s hospital

Some syntactic errors were identified in the initial test extractions:

- The tag “General treatment data” in specification is missing
- The tag “Anamnesis” is incorrect and should be replaced with “namnesis”
- The tag “Sex” is incorrect and should be replaced with “sex
- The tag “Age” is incorrect and should be replaced with “age
- The tag “ID” is incorrect and should be replaced with “idObject
- The tag “Medical visit entity” is incorrect and should be replaced with “medicalVisit”
- The tag “requestId” is incorrect and should be replaced with “requestId
- The tag “unitOfMeasure” is incorrect and should be replaced with “unitOfMeasureLabTest”

The correction of the errors was requested. However, as detailed in the periodic report, the Hospital withdrew from the project.

2.5.3. Outcome of the testing at hospital of Vercelli and Policlinico of Milan

In parallel with the analysis and proposal, the software provider (the same for Policlinico of Milan and hospital of Vercelli) shared a test data schema (see Annex 1 - D2.3 - Analisi_Progetto_ECREAM_ASL_VERCELLI attachment), in which some discrepancies were identified. In particular:

- The “revaluationList” field was expected to be a single element rather than an array.
- According to the specifications, some fields indicated as free text were limited to 400 characters. Through these tests, we found that restricting these fields to 400 characters was unnecessary. Therefore, the specifications were revised, and a new limit of 2000 characters was established.

The proposal was accepted, and implementation of the data extractions can now proceed.

2.5.4. Outcome of the testing at Sacco hospital, Milan

A test data file was provided, but it proved unusable due to incorrect JSON formatting. Additionally, there was no correspondence between episodes and JSON files as required by the agreed specifications. Numerous syntactic errors were also identified.

2.5.5. Outcome synthesis

The NLP, UC1, and UC2 protocols have been submitted and approved for the following hospitals:

Name of Hospital	Country	Province	ETHICS COMMITTEE APPROVALS			Test Outcomes
			PROTOCOL NLP	PROTOCOL UC1	PROTOCOL UC2	
Ospedale San Giovanni Bosco	Italy	Torino	approved	approved	approved	Completed
San Luigi Gonzaga	Italy	Orbassano	approved	approved	approved	Unscheduled
ASL Vercelli - Borgosesia- Ospedale Sant'Andrea	Italy	Vercelli	no needed approval	no needed approval	no needed approval	Completed
Policlinico Ospedale Maggiore	Italy	Milan	approved	approved	approved	Completed
ASST Sacco	Italy	Milan	approved	under review	under review	In progress
Ospedale Maggiore Carlo Alberto Pizzardi	Italy	Bologna	approved	approved	approved	To plan
Ente Ospedaliero Cantonale (EOC)	Swiss	Lugano	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Completed
AO SS. Antonio e Biagio e C. Arrigo	Italy	Alessandria	under review	under review	under review	Unscheduled
ASST Grande H Metropolitan Niguarda	Italy	Milan	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
San Martino	Italy	Genova	submitted	not submitted	not submitted	Unscheduled
ASL TO4, Ospedale di Chivasso	Italy	Chivasso	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
Ospedale degli Infermi	Italy	Rivoli	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
Ospedale Sant' Eugenio	Italy	Rome	submitted	not submitted	not submitted	Unscheduled
Ospedale Maggiore	Italy	Lodi	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
Ospedale Santa Maria Annunziata	Italy	Florence	submitted	not submitted	not submitted	Unscheduled
ASL Napoli 2- Santa Maria delle Grazie	Italy	Pozzuoli	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
Presidio Ospedaliero AOUP "G. Rodolico - San Marco"	Italy	Catania	approved	approved	approved	Unscheduled
Papa Giovanni XXIII	Italy	Bergamo	approved	under review	under review	Unscheduled
Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Safarika v Kosiciach	Slovakia	Košice	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Unscheduled
East Slovakian Cardiovascular Institute	Slovakia	Nové Mesto	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Unscheduled
L. Pasteur University Hospital	Slovakia	Košice	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Unscheduled
AGEL Hospital	Slovakia	Ružinov	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Unscheduled
Hospital Emergency Ward, Military Hospital	Poland	Kraków	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
Stefan Zeromsky Specialist Hospital	Poland	Kraków	no longer participating	no longer participating	no longer participating	Unscheduled
University Hospital Krakow	Poland	Kraków	approved	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
Ashford and St Peter's hospitals NHS foundation trust	UK	Surrey	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
Royal Surrey County Hospital	UK	Guildford	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
Frimley Park Hospital	UK	Camberley	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled

University General Hospital of Heraklion	Greece	Heraklion	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
General Hospital of Chania, St George	Greece	Chania	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
General Hospital of Rethymnon	Greece	Rethymnon	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
General Hospital "Venizeleio-Pananeio"	Greece	Heraklion	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
General Hospital of Agjos Nikolaos	Greece	Lasithi	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	not yet contacted	Unscheduled
UKC	Slovenia	Maribor	approved	approved	approved	Unscheduled

Figure 12. Outcomes' synthesis

In synthesis:

STATUS PROTOCOL	NLP PROTOCOL	UC1 PROTOCOL	UC2 PROTOCOL
approved	14	6	6
no longer participating	6	6	6
no needed approval	1	1	1
not yet contacted	9	3	3
submitted, not yet approved	3	10	10
under review	1	8	8
TOTAL	34	34	34

Figure 13. Protocol's status

Status protocol

Figure 14. Chart of protocol status

STATUS TEST	TEST OUTCOMES
Completed	4
Unscheduled	28
To plan	1
In progress	1
TOTAL	34

Figure 15. Summary of the data processed

Figure 15. Chart of test outcomes

A contact has been established with all the hospitals presented in the table, through the presentation of the eCREAM project and the sharing of technical specifications.

The eCREAM Local Client was installed at San Giovanni Bosco Hospital, Turin, Italy at San Luigi Gonzaga Hospital, Orbassano, Italy, Maggiore Carlo Alberto Pizzardi Hospital, Bologna, Italy and ASL Vercelli Sant'Andrea Hospital, Vercelli, Italy.

Data were extracted only from S.G. Bosco Hospital, Turin, Italy, and were imported into the local eCREAM model.

3. Interface modules of the new ED-EHR

The new ED-EHR is still under design and development, so the integration test has not yet been executed.

The integration between the new ED-EHR and the eCREAM platform will be implemented on the HL7 FHIR standard to guarantee seamless and accurate information flow across systems.

Data exchange will be managed through RESTful APIs compliant with the FHIR standard (<https://www.hl7.org/fhir/http.html>). These API calls will expose relevant FHIR resources (such as Patient, Encounter, Observation, etc.).

Besides the verification about the compliance of the gathered data with the eCREAM data model and their completeness, correctness and internal coherence, the tests will focus on validating:

- correct sending and receiving of API requests.
- appropriate handling of HTTP status codes.
- payload consistency and adherence to FHIR structure.
- authentication and authorization between systems.

4. Conclusion

The process of extracting and validating data from different hospitals highlighted the complexity and heterogeneity of the IT Systems used in Emergency Departments and the need for standardisation and semantic clarification of data to ensure quality and interoperability.

In detail:

- Structural and semantic differences between the formats used by different hospitals required careful analysis to harmonise the meaning of the fields.
- Syntactic errors and discrepancies with specifications were frequent in the early versions of the formats, with problems relating to tag nomenclature, JSON format, and incorrect use of fields such as “id” instead of “idObject”, which required corrective cycles with suppliers.
- The experience of Giovanni Bosco in Turin, the first centre to complete a supply in a production environment, made it possible to identify and resolve numerous critical issues, serving as a model for subsequent installations.
- The management of links to external reports (RIS, LIS, other EHRs) was successfully implemented through defined naming conventions to manage multiple examinations associated with the same request.
- Semantic ambiguities emerged for some fields, making it necessary to provide transcoding tables.
- The extraction of free text (clinical notes, nursing diary, triage, discharges) and the subsequent automatic anonymisation of PDF reports confirmed the technical feasibility of the NLP-DeVAL protocol, with the transformation of over 300,000 reports into anonymous text.
- Sacco and Lugano hospitals were unable to successfully complete the testing phase due to, respectively, unresolved technical issues or withdrawal from the project.

Overall, the work carried out so far permitted a refinement in the extraction and validation model, identifying critical points to be monitored in future installations and providing a replicable reference model for the adoption of the eCREAM platform at other centres.

The corrective actions implemented by Astir to extract data from PDF files (radiology, laboratory, and other reports) represented an important step toward ensuring the availability of information while respecting privacy, especially in contexts where direct integration with existing systems proved complex.

As a secondary result of the activity that involved Astir and the hospital IT Staff, including their IT suppliers, a solid network of contacts was established.

During the analysis phases, it was possible to identify the IT service representatives and establish direct dialogue with them and the suppliers to customize the rules for data extraction for each hospital.

These contacts will be very important throughout the entire duration of the project, to assist suppliers and hospital IT services with installation activities and data extraction.

To ensure effective support, Astir provided a dedicated project email address (wp2.ecream@astir.com) and a mailing list (wp2.ecream-list@astir.com), in addition to the direct contacts of Astir’s project representatives.

5. Annex

Annex 1 - D2.3 – “Analisi_Progetto_ECREAM_ASL_VERCELLI”

Analisi PS - eCREAM

Versione	Data Redazione	Redattore	Descrizione	Riesaminatore	Data Riesame
1.0	27/03/2025	Riccardo Andreucci	Analisi	Raffaele Schiavone	01/04/2025

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Scopo del Documento

Lo scopo del presente documento è illustrare la soluzione ottimale che soddisfa i requisiti descritti nel documento "Application Interface Specifications UC1 and UC2.pdf". In particolare, dettagliamo il formato e le modalità di compilazione di tutti gli elementi del tracciato.

Modalità di Estrazione

La richiesta riguarda l'estrazione una tantum di un tracciato completo di tutte le informazioni relative a ogni singolo episodio, registrate nel sistema di Pronto Soccorso dal 01/01/2021 al 31/12/2023. L'estrazione è rivolta ai pazienti dimessi che, durante la fase di triage, sono stati identificati con Dispnea o perdita temporanea di coscienza (TLOC). Il tracciato sarà depositato su un server, in una cartella concordata.

Nel nostro applicativo la condizione "pazienti dimessi che, durante la fase di triage, sono stati identificati con Dispnea o perdita temporanea di coscienza (TLOC)", si traduce con: campo "mainClinicalProblem" = 231- DISPNEA o 242 - PERDITA DI COSCIENZA.

Entity edEpisode

Di seguito, presentiamo il tracciato descritto nelle specifiche. In questo documento, analizzeremo nel dettaglio le singole sezioni, descrivendo il formato dei dati estratti dai nostri sistemi e, quando necessario, fornendo ulteriori dettagli sulle nostre codifiche.

```
{  
  "episode": {episode},  
  "triage": {triage},  
  "turnaroundTime": null,  
  "pathAssignmentList": [{pathAssignment}],  
  "revaluationList": [{revaluation}],  
  "anamnesis": "anamnesis",  
  "homeBasedTherapy": "homeBasedTherapy",  
  "medicalVisitList ": [{medicalVisit}],  
  "nursingCareStart": null,  
  "imagingTestList": [{imagingTest}],  
  "labTestList": [{labTest}],  
  "otherTestList": [{otherTest}],  
  "vitalParametersList": [{vitalParameter}],  
}
```

Analisi

```
"nursingCareNotesList": [{nursingCareNote}],
"clinicalDiaryList": [{clinicalDiary}],
"medicalProcedureList": [{medicalProcedure}],
"specialistConsultancyList": [{specialistConsultancy}],
"pharmaceuticalTherapyList": [{pharmaceuticalTherapy}],
"respiratorySupportList": [{respiratorySupport}],
"monitoringList": [{monitoring}],
"discharge": {discharge},
"obsUnit": {obsUnit}
}
```

Episode entity

```
{
  "organizationCode": "010009",
  "emergencyDepartmentId": "010082",
  "episodeld": "202220834",
  "edArrivalDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "sex": "M",
  "age": "35",
  "arrivalModeCode": "2"
}
```

dove:

- **"organizationCode": "010009"**
- **"emergencyDepartmentId":**
 - Vercelli: "010082"
 - Borgosesia: "010086"
- **"episodeld": anno + n. pratica**
- **"edArrivalDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:13:23"**
- **sex:**
 - Maschio: "M"
 - Femmina: "F"
- **"age": "35"**
- **arrivalModeCode:**
 - 1: MEDICO DI BASE
 - 2: GUARDIA MEDICA
 - 3: MEZZI PROPRI
 - 5: BLS (Basic Life Support)
 - 6: ALS (Advanced Life Support - 118)

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- 7: ELISOCCORSO (118)
- 8: CASA CIRCONDARIALE
- 10: TRASFERITO DA ISTITUTO PUBBLICO
- 11: TRASFERITO DA PRIVATO ACCREDITATO O PROVVISORIAMENTE ACCREDITATO
- 12: TRASFERITO DA PRIVATO NON ACCREDITATO
- 13: TRASFERITO DA RSA-RAF - Ospedale di comunità
- 14: METAL

Triage entity

```
{  
  "triageDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:18:23",  
  "triagePriority": "3",  
  "triageNotes": "epistassi sx da ieri pregresso episodio un paio d'anni fa. si presenta  
  con tampone nasale. anamnesi nds. allergie nds. vigile, orientato, collaborante  
  percorso covid free",  
  "mainClinicalProblem": "14",  
  "secondaryClinicalProblem": "con nausea, con parestesie, con rigidita' nucale  
  obiettiva"  
}
```

- **"triagePriority":**
 - 1: Codice rosso
 - 2: Codice arancione
 - 3: Codice azzurro
 - 4: Codice verde
 - 5: Codice bianco
- **triageNotes:** Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 400 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.
- **mainClinicalProblem:**
 - 224: ALTERAZIONI DEL RITMO
 - 225: ALTRO
 - 226: AVVELENAMENTO
 - 227: CARDIOPALMO
 - 228: CEFALEA
 - 229: CRISI IPERTENSIVA
 - 230: DIARREA
 - 231: DISPNEA
 - 232: DOLORE ADDOMINALE

Analisi

- 233: DOLORE LOMBARE
 - 234: DOLORE NON TRAUMATICO
 - 235: DOLORE TORACICO
 - 236: EMORRAGIE DIGESTIVE
 - 237: FEBBRE
 - 238: FERITE
 - 239: GINECOLOGIA
 - 240: INTOSSICAZIONE
 - 241: ITTERO
 - 242: PERDITA DI COSCIENZA
 - 243: PROBLEMA SOCIALE
 - 244: REAZIONE ALLERGICA
 - 245: SINTOMI O DISTURBI OCULISTICI
 - 246: SINTOMI O DISTURBI OTORINOLARINGOIATRICI
 - 247: SINTOMI O DISTURBI UROLOGICI
 - 248: STATO DI AGITAZIONE
 - 249: TRAUMA
 - 250: USTIONE
 - 251: VERTIGINI
 - 252: VIOLENZA
 - 253: VOMITO
- **"secondaryClinicalProblem"**: Testo libero. Concatenazione di sintomi secondari scelti dai pannelli. Nell'applicazione di PS i sintomi secondari sono gestiti tramite checkbox.

TurnaroundTime

Il dato di libero barella non viene registrato a sistema.

PathAssignment entity

Il dato non viene registrato a sistema.

Revaluation entity

```
{  
  "idObject": "130924",  
  "revaluationTime": "2022-06-22T16:18:23",  
  "newPriorityLevel ": "2"  
}
```

Analisi

dove:

- **idObject**: id del record di rivalutazione
- **revaluationTime**: ora inserimento record di rivalutazione
- **newPriorityLevel**: codice della nuova priorità assegnata al paziente

Anamnesis

Il dato non viene registrato a sistema

HomeBasedTherapy

Il dato non viene registrato a sistema

MedicalVisit entity

Questa entità verrà popolata con tutti i dati visita del paziente. Quindi:

- Anamnesi
- Esame Obiettivo
- Terapia in atto
- Allergie e intolleranze

Per ogni tipologia di dato potrebbero esserci record multipli.

Ma verranno tutti costruiti in rispetto del modello in specifica.

```
{
  "idObject": "123_1",
  "dateTimeMedicalVisit": "2022-06-22T17:13:23",
  "medicalVisitOutcome": "Fibrosi polmonare da amiodarone (Avrebbe avuto in programma una valutazione pneumologica c/o l'H Sacco oggi){FAP in terapia anticoagulante{Portatrice di PM per sindrome bradi-tachi{Ipertensione arteriosa{Nega storia di cardiopatia ischemica{{Vaccinata con 3 dosi di vaccino per COVID-19"
},
{
  "idObject": "124_2",
  "dateTimeMedicalVisit": "2022-06-22T17:19:23",
  "medicalVisitOutcome": "- Ipertensione{- Dislipidemia{- Diabete Mellito{- Intervento Ernia del disco {- Extrasistolia ventricolare e sopraventricolare paucisintomatica. Ultimo ecocardiogramma eseguito nel 2016, riferito nella norma {{Vive sola{{Vaccinata SARS-CoV2 3 dosi"
```

Analisi

}

dove:

- **idObject**: Dato che nell'applicativo di PS l'univocità è garantita solo per tipologia di dato visita (Anamnesi, Esame Obiettivo, Terapia in atto, Allergie e intolleranze), per renderlo univoco utilizziamo la convenzione:

```
{id_record}+"_"+{cod_tipologia_dato_visita}
```

dove:

- ❖ *id_record* è l'id del record registrato su Database
- ❖ *cod_tipologia_dato_visita*
 - 1: Anamnesi
 - 2: Esame Obiettivo
 - 3: Terapia in atto
 - 4: Allergie e intolleranze
- **dateTimeMedicalVisit**: Data di validazione del dato, ovvero istante in cui il medico inserisce le proprie credenziali per firmare il dato inserito a sistema.
- **medicalVisitOutcome**: Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

NursingCareStart

Il dato non viene registrato a sistema

ImagingTest entity

Implementeremo la soluzione Case B:

```
{  
  "requestId": "010009_202220834_2740057",  
  "idObject": "4699357"  
}
```

dove:

- **requestId**: Campo costruito dalla concatenazione tra il Codice dell'Organizzazione, l'evento del Pronto Soccorso (episodeld) e il numero di richiesta.
es: 010009_202220834_2740057
- **idObject**: id univoco es.4699357. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento al referto comunicato dal dipartimentale.

Analisi

LabTest entity

Implementeremo la soluzione Case B:

```
{  
  "requestId": "010009_202220834_2740058"  
  "idObject": "2740058"  
}
```

dove:

- **requestId**: Campo costruito dalla concatenazione tra il Codice dell'Organizzazione, l'evento del Pronto Soccorso (episodeld) e il numero di richiesta.
es: 010009_202220834_2740058
- **idObject**: id univoco es.4699358. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento al referto comunicato dal dipartimentale.

OtherTestList

Dato non registrato.

Questa entità viene popolata con i referti delle consulenze di Pronto Soccorso. In questo caso implementeremo la soluzione CASE A, dato che le consulenze vengono richieste e anche refertate direttamente sull'applicazione di PS, quindi il dato è di nostra gestione.

```
{  
  "requestId": "010009_202220834_2740059",  
  "idObject": "4699359",  
  "dateTimeRequestOtherTest": "2022-06-22T19:13:23",  
  "dateTimeOtherTestExecution": null,  
  "dateTimeOtherTestReport": "2022-06-22T21:15:23",  
  "otherTestCode": "N_MECAU_14"  
  "otherTestReportText": "Polimialgie diffuse. Alle Rx non patologie discali lombari. ritengo trattarsi di polimialgia in quadro fibromialgico. Farei Deltacortene 25 mg cps per 2 volte die per 5 gg 1/2 per 2 per altri 5 gg poi Deltacortene 5 MGT CPS 1 PER DUE PER 5 GG poi 5 mg 1 volta die per 30 gg. Gastroprotezione per 2 mesi. Laroxyl gocce 4 gocce al mattino"
```

dove:

- **requestId**: Costruito come nei casi precedenti. Concatenazione tra il Codice dell'Organizzazione, l'evento del Pronto Soccorso (episodeld) e il numero di richiesta
- **idObject**: id univoco es.4699359. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento al referto testuale.

Analisi

- **dateTimeRequestOtherTest**: Data inserimento richiesta visita di consulenza sull'applicazione di Pronto Soccorso.
- **dateTimeOtherTestExecution**: Sempre null. Dato non gestito in PS.
- **dateTimeOtherTestReport**: Data validazione della consulenza. Istante in cui il medico inserisce le credenziali per validare il referto.
- **otherTestCode**: Forniremo la tabella anagrafica delle prestazioni richiedibili da PS. Completa di codice e descrizione delle prestazioni.
- **otherTestReportText**: Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

VitalParameter entity

```
{  
  "idObject": "1099676",  
  "dateTimeDetection": "2022-06-22T20:13:23",  
  "systolicPressure": "120",  
  "diastolicPressure": "60",  
  "heartRate": "95",  
  "respiratoryRate": "14",  
  "bodyTemperature": "38",  
  "spO2": "95",  
  "levelConsciousness": "2",  
  "vitalParametersText": "EGA MOD. : Aria Ambiente - DIURESIS TOTALE : 500 -  
SATURAZIONE : 93%"  
}
```

dove:

- **idObject**: id univoco es.1099676. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento alla rilevazione di parametri vitali.
- **dateTimeDetection**: data raccolta della rilevazione dei parametri vitali.
- **systolicPressure**: Pressione massima.
- **diastolicPressure**: Pressione minima.
- **heartRate**: frequenza cardiaca.
- **respiratoryRate**: frequenza respiratoria.
- **bodyTemperature**: temperatura corporea.
- **spO2**: Percentuale ossigeno nel sangue.
- **levelConsciousness**:
 - 1 - COSCIENTE

Analisi

- 2 - RISP. CHIAMATA
- 3 - RISP. DOLORE
- 4 - NON COSCIENTE
- 5 - GIUNTO CADAVERE
- **vitalParametersText:** Riportiamo la concatenazione dei restanti parametri vitali raccolti con le rispettive unità di misura, separati da "-". Troncato a 400 caratteri.

NursingCareNote entity

```
{  
  "idObject": "1507824",  
  "dateTimeNote": "2022-06-22T20:13:23",  
  "nursingNote": " Previa disinfezione ed analgesia si applicano due punti di  
  avvicinamento con filo di seta 4-0"  
}
```

dove:

- **idObject:** id univoco es.1099676. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento alla nota del diario infermieristico.
- **dateTimeNote:** data salvataggio nota diario infermieristico.
- **nursingNote:** Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

ClinicalDiary entity

```
{  
  "idObject": "1509378",  
  "dateTimeClinicalDiary": "2022-06-22T20:20:23",  
  "clinicalDiary": " "paziente soporoso ma risvegliabile alla chiamata, addome trattabile,  
  non dolente alla palpazione superficiale e profonda. toni cardiaci validi, tachiaritmici.  
  mv abolito alle basi con crepitii inspiratori bibasali. edemi duri agli arti inferiori, cute  
  secca  
  contattato cardiologo e rianimatore per rivalutazione e per eventuale ecocardiografia  
  transesofagea nell'ottica di eseguire CVE"  
}
```

dove:

- **idObject:** id univoco es.1509378. Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento alla nota del diario clinico.
- **dateTimeNote:** data salvataggio nota diario clinico.

Analisi

- **nursingNote:** Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

MedicalProcedure entity

Viene estratta la lista di tutte le prestazioni richieste da un profilo medico. Vengono estratte anche le prestazioni di Laboratorio e radiologia, dato che nelle sezioni precedenti "ImagingTest entity" e "LabTest entity" non viene estratto il dettaglio della prestazione.

```
{  
  "idObject": "8612505",  
  "dateTimeRequestMedicalProcedure": "2022-06-22T19:13:23",  
  "dateTimeExecutionMedicalProcedure": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",  
  "medicalProcedureCode": "PS345492"  
}
```

dove:

- **idObject:** 8612505
- **dateTimeRequestMedicalProcedure:** Data inserimento prestazione.
- **dateTimeExecutionMedicalProcedure:** Data dell'appuntamento. Trattandosi di Pronto Soccorso questa data, nella maggior parte dei casi, coincide con dateTimeRequestMedicalProcedure.
- **medicalProcedureCode:** Forniremo la tabella anagrafica delle prestazioni richiedibili da PS. Completa di codice e descrizione delle prestazioni.

SpecialistConsultancy entity

Questa entità viene popolata con i referti delle consulenze di Pronto Soccorso. In questo caso implementeremo la soluzione CASE A, dato che le consulenze vengono richieste e anche refertate direttamente sull'applicazione di PS.

Case A:

```
{  
  "requestId": "010009_202220834_2740059",  
  "idObject": "4699359",  
  "consultancyType": "VISITA CARDIOLOGICA (89.7)",  
  "dateTimeSpecialistConsultancy": "2023-06-22T15:14:18",  
  "reportTextSpecialistConsultancy": "Polimialgie diffuse. Alle Rx non patologie discali lombari. ritengo trattarsi di polimialgia in quadro fibromialgico. Farei Deltacortene 25 mg cps per 2 volte die per 5 gg 1/2 per 2 per altri 5 gg poi Deltacortene 5 MGT CPS
```

Analisi

1 PER DUE PER 5 GG poi 5 mg 1 volta die per 30 gg. Gastroprotezione per 2 mesi.
Laroxyl gocce 4 gocce al mattino"

}

dove:

- **requestId**: Costruito come nei casi precedenti. Concatenazione tra il Codice dell'Organizzazione, l'evento del Pronto Soccorso (episodeld) e il numero di richiesta.
- **idObject**: Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento alla prestazione.
- **consultancyType**: Non gestiamo la tipologia di consulenza; passiamo la descrizione della prestazione.
- **dateTimeSpecialistConsultancy**: Data inserimento richiesta visita di consulenza sull'applicazione di Pronto Soccorso.
- **reportTextSpecialistConsultancy**: Testo libero. Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

PharmaceuticalTherapy entity

{

```
"idObject": "1063968",  
"dateTimeTherapyPrescription": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",  
"dateTimeTherapyAdministration": "2022-06-22T18:13:23",  
"therapyType": "Paracetamolo 1 gr"
```

}

dove:

- **idObject**: Id record di registrazione su DB del riferimento al farmaco.
- **dateTimeTherapyPrescription**: Data inserimento richiesta farmaco sull'applicazione di Pronto Soccorso.
- **dateTimeTherapyAdministration**: Data somministrazione farmaco.
- **therapyType**: Descrizione del farmaco richiesto. Sul PS è un campo a testo libero.

RespiratorySupport entity

Dato non gestito su PS.

Monitoring entity

Dato non gestito su PS.

Analisi

Discharge entity

```
{  
    "dischargeDecisionDateTime": "2022-06-22T23:00:00",  
    "dischargeDateTime": "2022-06-22T23:45:23",  
    "modeOfExit": "30",  
    "diagnosisAtEDDischarge": "OSTEOMIELETTE CRONICA, OMER",  
    "dischargeNotes": "Veda consulenza urologica per indicazioni.  
Consiglio: cefixoral 400 mg una cp al giorno per 5 giorni. Si rilascia impegnativa per  
visita malattie Orto-infettive per controllo in possibile osteomielite piede dx ed  
impegnativa per tentativo rimozione catetere vescicale il 14.04.Si consiglia:-  
Eseguire visita gastroenterologica (già in possesso della richiesta).- Se dolore,  
paracetamolo 500 mg ogni 8 ore associato a buscopan 1 cp ogni 8 ore.- Cefixoral  
400 mg/die per 5 giorni.- Controllo evolutivo dal medico curante.A disposizione.NON  
acuzie al momento della dimissione. Riferire al proprio MMG curante."  
}  
}
```

dove:

- **dischargeDecisionDateTime:** Data e ora inserimento Dimissibilità del paziente. Gestiamo varie tipologie di dimissibilità, non solo la dimissibilità in attesa di posto letto o in attesa del mezzo per trasferimento verso altro ospedale. Quindi l'informazione potrebbe essere valorizzata anche in altre tipologie di dimissione. (ad es. Dimissibile in attesa di parenti o semplicemente Dimissibile al domicilio).
- **dischargeDateTime:** Data e ora dimissione paziente.
- **modeOfExit:**

Modalità di dimissione:

- 27 SI E' ALLONTANATO (PRIMA DELLA VISITA)
- 28 IL PAZIENTE RIFIUTA IL RICOVERO
- 29 RICOVERATO
- 30 DIMESSO, INVIATO AL CURANTE
- 31 TRASFERITO IN ALTRO PS STESSA ASL
- 32 TRASFERITO AD ALTRA STRUTTURA DI RICOVERO
- 33 TRASFERITO IN ALTRA STUTTURA (RSA-RAF-OSP.DI COMUNITA')
- 34 SI E' ALLONTANATO (DOPO LA VISITA)
- 35 DECEDUTO
- 36 DIMISSIONE VOLONTARIA
- 37 GIUNTO CADAVERE
- 39 DIMESSO, INVIATO ALLO SPECIALISTA

Analisi

se paziente OBI:

- 15 IL PAZIENTE RIFIUTA IL RICOVERO
 - 16 RICOVERATO
 - 17 DIMESSO, INVIATO AL CURANTE
 - 18 TRASFERITO IN ALTRO PS STESSA ASL
 - 19 TRASFERITO AD ALTRA STRUTTURA DI RICOVERO
 - 20 TRASFERITO IN ALTRA STUTTURA (RSA-RAF-OSP.DI
COMUNITA')
 - 21 SI E' ALLONTANATO (DOPO LA VISITA)
 - 22 DECEDUTO
 - 23 DIMISSIONE VOLONTARIA
 - 24 GIUNTO CADAVERE
 - 26 DIMESSO, INVIATO ALLO SPECIALISTA
- **diagnosisAtEDDischarge**: Estratta solo la descrizione della diagnosi principale di uscita da Pronto Soccorso.
 - **dischargeNotes**: Concatenazione delle note registrate per i campi:
 - Stato paziente alla dimissione
 - Terapia alla dimissione
 - Piano di assistenza alla dimissione

Sul nostro applicativo accettiamo testi anche molto più lunghi di 2000 caratteri, quindi verrà troncato per esigenze del sistema ricevente.

ObsUnit entity

```
{  
  "decisionObsUnit":null,  
  "transferObsUnit": "2022-06-22T23:30:23",  
  "exitObsUnit": "2022-06-22T23:50:23"  
}
```

dove:

- **decisionObsUnit**: Dato non gestito
- **transferObsUnit**: Data di ingresso in OBI
- **exitObsUnit**: Data dimissione da OBI

Tracciato completo di esempio

```
{
```

 Certificato Nr. 3917365-1			
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Analisi

```
"episode": {
  "organizationCode": "010009",
  "emergencyDepartmentId": "010082",
  "episodeId": "202220834",
  "edArrivalDateTime": "22-06-22T15:13:23",
  "sex": "M",
  "age": "35",
  "arrivalModeCode": "2"
},
"triage": {
  "triageDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:18:23",
  "triagePriority": "3",
  "triageNotes": "epistassi sx da ieri pregresso episodio un paio d'anni fa. si
presenta con tampone nasale. anamnesi nds. allergie nds. vigile, orientato, collaborante
percorso covid free",
  "mainClinicalProblem": "14",
  "secondaryClinicalProblem": "con nausea, con parestesie, con rigidita' nucale
obiettiva"
},
"turnaroundTime": null,
"pathAssignmentList": null,
"reevaluationList": {
  "idObject": "130924",
  "reevaluationTime": "2022-06-22T16:18:23",
  "newPriorityLevel": "2"
},
"anamnesis": null,
"homeBasedTherapy": null,
"medicalVisitList": [
  {
    "idObject": "123_1",
    "dateTimeMedicalVisit": "2022-06-22T17:13:23",
    "medicalVisitOutcome": "Fibrosi polmonare da amiodarone (Avrebbe
avuto in programma una valutazione pneumologica c/o l'H Sacco oggi){FAP in terapia
anticoagulante{Portatrice di PM per sindrome bradi-tachi{Ipertensione arteriosa{Nega storia
di cardiopatia ischemica{{Vaccinata con 3 dosi di vaccino per COVID-19"
  },
  {
    "idObject": "124_2",
```

Analisi

```
"dateTimeMedicalVisit": "2022-06-22T17:19:23",
"medicalVisitOutcome": "- Ipertensione{- Dislipidemia{- Diabete
Mellito{- Intervento Ernia del disco {- Extrasistolia ventricolare e sopraventricolare
paucisintomatica. Ultimo ecocardiogramma eseguito nel 2016, riferito nella norma {{Vive
sola{{Vaccinata SARS-CoV2 3 dosi"
}
],
"nursingCareStart": null,
"imagingTestList": [
{
"requestId": "010009_202220834_2740057",
"idObject": "4699357"
},
{
"requestId": "010009_202220834_2740058",
"idObject": "4699358"
}
],
"labTestList": [
{
"requestId": "010009_202220834_2740059",
"idObject": "2740059"
},
{
"requestId": "010009_202220834_2740060",
"idObject": "2740060"
}
],
"otherTestList": null,
"vitalParametersList": [
{
"objectId": "1099676",
"dateTimeDetection": "2022-06-22T20:13:23",
"systolicPressure": "120",
"diastolicPressure": "60",
"heartRate": "95",
"respiratoryRate": "14",
"bodyTemperature": "38",
"spO2": "95",
```

Analisi

```
"levelConsciousness": "2",
  "vitalParametersText": "EGA MOD. : Aria Ambiente - DIURESI
TOTALE : 500 - SATURAZIONE : 93%"
},
"nursingCareNotesList": [
  {
    "idObject": "1507824",
    "dateTimeNote": "2022-06-22T20:13:23",
    "nursingNote": "Prevista disinfezione ed analgesia, si applicano due
punti di avvicinamento con filo di seta 4-0."
  }
],
"clinicalDiaryList": [
  {
    "idObject": "1509378",
    "dateTimeClinicalDiary": "2022-06-22T20:20:23",
    "clinicalDiary": "paziente soporoso ma risvegliabile alla chiamata,
addome trattabile, non dolente alla palpazione superficiale e profonda. toni cardiaci validi,
tachiaritmici. mv abolito alle basi con crepitii inspiratori bibasali. edemi duri agli arti inferiori,
cute secca. contattato cardiologo e rianimatore per rivalutazione e per eventuale
ecocardiografia transesofagea nell'ottica di eseguire CVE."
  }
],
"medicalProcedureList": [
  {
    "idObject": "8612505",
    "dateTimeRequestMedicalProcedure": "2022-06-22T19:13:23",
    "dateTimeExecutionMedicalProcedure": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
    "medicalProcedureCode": "PS345492"
  }
],
"specialistConsultancyList": [
  {
    "requestId": "010009_202220834_2740059",
    "idObject": "4699359",
    "consultancyType": "VISITA CARDIOLOGICA (89.7)",
    "dateTimeSpecialistConsultancy": "2023-06-22T15:14:18",
```

Analisi

"reportTextSpecialistConsultancy": "Polimialgie diffuse. Alle Rx non patologie discali lombari. Ritengo trattarsi di polimialgia in quadro fibromialgico. Farei Deltacortene 25 mg cps per 2 volte die per 5 gg, 1/2 per 2 per altri 5 gg, poi Deltacortene 5 mg cps 1 per due per 5 gg, poi 5 mg 1 volta die per 30 gg. Gastroprotezione per 2 mesi. Laroxyl gocce 4 gocce al mattino."

```
    }
  ],
  "pharmaceuticalTherapyList": [
    {
      "idObject": "1063968",
      "dateTimeTherapyPrescription": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
      "dateTimeTherapyAdministration": "2022-06-22T18:13:23",
      "therapyType": "Paracetamolo 1 gr"
    }
  ],
  "respiratorySupportList": null,
  "monitoringList": null,
  "discharge": {
    "dischargeDecisionDateTime": "2022-06-22T23:00:00",
    "dischargeDateTime": "2022-06-22T23:45:23",
    "modeOfExit": "30",
    "diagnosisAtEDDischarge": "OSTEOMIELITE CRONICA, OMER",
    "dischargeNotes": "Veda consulenza urologica per indicazioni. Consiglio:
cefixoral 400 mg una cp al giorno per 5 giorni. Si rilascia impegnativa per visita malattie
Orto-infettive per controllo in possibile osteomielite piede dx ed impegnativa per tentativo
rimozione catetere vescicale il 14.04. Si consiglia: - Eseguire visita gastroenterologica (già in
possesso della richiesta). - Se dolore, paracetamolo 500 mg ogni 8 ore associato a
buscopan 1 cp ogni 8 ore. - Cefixoral 400 mg/die per 5 giorni. - Controllo evolutivo dal
medico curante. A disposizione. NON acuzie al momento della dimissione. Riferire al proprio
MMG curante."
  },
  "obsUnit": {
    "decisionObsUnit": null,
    "transferObsUnit": "2022-06-22T23:30:23",
    "exitObsUnit": "2022-06-22T23:50:23"
  }
}
```